

Characteristics and Necessity of Developing Students' Communicative Competence

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of communicative competence in the comprehensive development of students, the specific aspects of the development of communicative competence, as well as the importance of communicative competence in reforming the "teacher-student" relationship in the pedagogical process of the school.

Keywords: Communicativeness, general secondary education, student, competence, school practice, ability, personality development, reflection.

Currently, according to the demands placed on the entire educational system, it is necessary to improve the preparation of future personnel for professional and communicative activities, that is, their professional qualifications, the ability to quickly adapt to changing conditions, communicative competence, communicative knowledge, skills of continuous independent filling their communicative competence and creative usage of them should be developed. For this purpose, it is appropriate to prepare students for communicative activities from the general secondary education process in order to form various competencies in them.

Increasing the effectiveness of education from the lower stages of education, which is valued as a unique capital, introducing improved mechanisms, preparing students for communicative activities in the future life as a result of quality education is the main part and considered one of the tasks of the educational process of general secondary schools. At a time when the importance of research on organizing the processes of effective preparation for social life through the formation of practical activity experience and the formation of various competences among students of general secondary education is increasing, the development of communicative competence among students is also relevant.

It should be noted that nowadays the competence approach is widely used in the teaching of various subjects. It has also been proved that it is not enough to give them knowledge, skills, and skills related to science, and that it is necessary to form the practical application of the acquired knowledge, skills, and skills in various situations. For this reason, the demand for competencies has penetrated into all stages of continuous education and is being used in practice.

In the course of the research, in order to clarify the content of the work in detail, it was aimed to analyze the opinions of scientists regarding the content of "competency" and "communicative competence" and highlight its specific features.

In modern scientific literature in developed countries, it is emphasized that the results of education are determined not only through knowledge, skills and abilities, but also through the

competences acquired by a person during the educational process. Competence is formed on the basis of the planned goal of the educational process, methods, technology and the qualification of the learner.

"Competence" is a Latin word that means to achieve, to be right. Competence is the person's readiness to effectively organize external and internal opportunities to set a goal and achieve it, the personal ability to solve certain professional issues.

"The concept of competence as components includes knowledge, skills and personal qualities (initiative, purposefulness, ability to set goals, responsibility, tolerance, etc.), social adaptation (ability to work in a team and outside of it), critical thinking ", as well as professional experience in the chosen field.

Pedagogical scientists R. Safarova and R. Jorayev proposed the following definition of the concept of competence (Lat. compete-erishyan, I am worthy):

- 1) scope of powers, rights and duties of a specific state body (local self-governing body) or official defined by law, charter and other documents;
- 2) knowledge, experience in one or another field;
- 3) a person's awareness of a certain area, the level of knowledge of this area.

According to N.M. Muslimov, the dictionary meaning of the English concept of "competence" means "ability", but "the term competence serves to express knowledge, skill, mastery and ability".

Professor B.Kh. Khodzhayev emphasized that the content of most of the definitions given to the concept of "competence" is related to professional education and professional activity, connecting this concept with general secondary education, "competence is in a certain field is defined as "exceeding the social requirements (norms) imposed on the student's educational preparation, which is necessary for effective productive activity".

According to K. J. Riskulova, "competence" means a set of professional laws, principles, requirements, rules, duties, tasks and obligations, as well as personal deontological norms, necessary for the holder of this or that profession.

The research work serves to study and analyze the essence of the concept of "communicative competence" from a pedagogical point of view, and to further illuminate the content of the research.

In the age of innovative information, using information as widely as possible, being able to manage it within the limits of one's own wishes and needs requires the implementation of active communicative relations with different people. Today, the flow of information that surrounds us requires everyone to search for the necessary information, extract and assimilate the information that is useful for him for the educational process and daily life to be meaningful and successful. In this case, it is necessary to know several languages, to understand the importance of using the language in practical activities, and to acquire communicative competence, which is recognized as an important element of basic competences.

Communicative competence - including the possession of complex communication skills, is studied in such areas as cultural norms and constraints on communication, knowledge, education, communication field, customs, etiquette, etiquette and professional affiliation.

Communicative competence is a general communicative characteristic of a person, which includes communication skills, knowledge, skills and abilities, emotional and social experience in the field of various communications.

In turn, communicative skill consists of:

- to provide a socio-psychological forecast of the communicative situation in which it is necessary to communicate;
- socio-psychological programming of the communication process, based on the uniqueness of the communicative situation;
- implementation of socio-psychological management of communication processes in a communicative situation.

Communicative competence is an integral quality that synthesizes general culture and its specific manifestations in professional activity. One of the conditions of communicative competence is the fulfillment of certain rules and requirements. The most important of these rules are:

- 1) general rule - if this idea is not understood or not fully understood, it is impossible to establish communication;
- 2) the rule of constant preparation for understanding - there are often semantic and personal barriers, which often lead to incomplete and incorrect understanding of messages;
- 3) the rule of precision - avoiding unknown, ambiguous words and using foreign or highly specialized terms depending on the situation;
- 4) the rule of control of signals - it is not enough to control only the content of the speech and message. In addition, his external escort is the control of his form in the part related to facial expressions, gestures, intonation and posture.
- 5) the rule of place and time - implying that the effectiveness of any message increases sharply when choosing the most appropriate situation to be implemented on time;
- 6) the rule of openness - to be ready to revise one's point of view under the influence of new situations, as well as to accept and take into account the point of view of the interlocutor;
- 7) the rule of active and constructive listening is the main condition of effective communication;
- 8) the rule of feedback - this ensures the achievement of the main goal of the communicative process, that is, mutual understanding.

The basis of communicative competence is formed by:

- ✓ organization of communication;
- ✓ interpersonal communication skills;
- ✓ maintaining communication, contact, establishing feedback;
- ✓ analysis of communication results.

The educational system of the modern society, which has a wide information space, demands communicativeness from students. In this regard, it is expected to rapidly develop high technologies of language teaching, within the framework of which communication skills will be developed. Also, one of the most important priorities of modern society is recognized as the possession of communicative competence of a person. The development of each student as a person, self-awareness and personal growth, formation, his positive self-understanding, first of all, depends on the level of formation of personal communicative competence.

The teacher, first of all, should pay attention to the fact that the student's communicative competence may be formed or partially formed, and it should be taken into account in its further development. Also, based on the age of the students and the specific characteristics of

teaching, it is necessary to carry out diagnostics of the formation of communicative competence step by step.

There are specific aspects of formation of communicative competence in general secondary education, which mainly depends directly on the psychological characteristics of students and the pedagogical environment.

Determining the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the formation of students' communicative competence allows to create a methodology based on personal and group characteristics of the team. Thus, it will be effective to choose specific methods of forming students' communicative competence.

Today, language teaching and education are aimed at supporting the child's development and self-development. With the transition to such a paradigm of education, qualitatively new demands are placed on the teacher.

So, what kind of teaching specialists do we need in the formation and development of new school language teaching? Pedagogical education requires specialists who understand the child's inner world, strive to create communicative relationships, and are ready for sufficient pedagogical communication with children. In order to maximize the student's abilities, to ensure his emotional freedom during the school process, it is necessary to reflect the professional humanitarian status of the teacher in his ideological views.

From this point of view, our state is paying more attention to mutual relations in education. Understanding each other is considered the most effective method in pedagogy, in which the most complete aspiration of relations is achieved, participants agree on their positions through dialogue, which is the main form of communication. The need for teachers who are able to acquire humaneness towards students and perform their professional tasks through communication poses the problem of purposeful development of teachers of future communicative competence.

It shows that the problem of communicative competence is important for the science of modern pedagogy and educational practice. Despite the theoretical development of the problem, it cannot be said that the "teacher-student" relationship undergoes fundamental changes in the pedagogical process of the school. We can see that this problem is important for modern pedagogic science and educational practice. It shows that the teacher should be a cultured pedagogue with moral behavior and a high level of communication culture for his students.

While studying the situation of this problem, we come across a number of conflicting situations and they are as follows:

- 1) traditional approach to interaction with children;
- 2) the modern school needs teachers who can engage in practical communication;
- 3) the ability to create the desire of students to work effectively with teachers.

Why or why do we need communicative competence in such a contradictory situation?

The application of communicativeness from the social practice of the individual to the whole large practice, and the second definition leads to the narrowing of the understanding of communicativeness without reason. Part of human culture is communicative attitude. Communicative competence problems that need to be solved in social life, students can acquire communicative experience by reading literature works, going to the theater or watching a movie. Communicative competence regulates the system of a person's relationship to themselves, to events occurring in the natural and social world.

What are the tasks of communicative competence? One of the tasks is to have the knowledge resources necessary to adequately analyze and interpret situations. Another way to learn

communicative competence is to observe organized games using technical means or try using these games during the lesson, and analyze the obtained information in a group.

In general, it can be said that communicative competence is defined as the ability to establish and effectively use and maintain relationships with other people, and competence is a set of knowledge, skills, and abilities that ensure effective communication. This type of competency involves the conscious experience of understanding and responding to communication partners through direct interaction. The process of improvement of communicative competence is connected with the development of personality.

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